

Supplementary File

Title: Generative AI for Software Project Management: Insights from a Review of Software Practitioner Literature

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1. Detailed Review Procedure

Methodology:

Grey Literature Review (We carried out a grey literature review as practitioners are heavily discussing the trend of using GenAI in software project management)

Data Collection

1. **Data Sources:** Blog posts, articles on professional networks such as LinkedIn, and industry reports that are publicly available and freely accessible on the internet.
2. **Search Tool:** Google
3. **Search Strings**

Initial Search String	("Generative Artificial Intelligence" OR "GenAI" OR "Generative AI") AND ("Agile software project management"* OR "software project management" OR "IT Project Management")
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Results: 467,000

**"Agile software project management" was used as a keyword to expand the number of search results as the majority of software practitioners adopt agile as their PM methodology [1].*

- Modified search string referring to similar literature.

Modified Search String	("Generative Artificial Intelligence" OR "GenAI" OR "Generative AI" OR "ChatGPT" OR "Co-Pilot" OR "Large Language Models" OR "LLMs") AND ("Agile software project management" OR "software project management" OR "IT Project Management")
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Results: 618,000

*“ChatGPT” and “Co-Pilot” were used as keywords to expand the number of search results as they are reported to be popular GenAI tools in current context [2].

4. Data Filtering (publication date and language filtering using Advanced search tool)

- o Date between 01/12/2022 (after ChatGPT release) to 01/05/2025 (study date)
- o Language must be English

Results: 38,700

5. Filtering based on article type:

- o Only the LinkedIn articles, blogs, and reports that have sufficient details for thematic analysis were taken while ignoring short posts or comments.

Results: 15,400

6. Topic filtering:

- o We manually reviewed only the top 5 pages of Google results as they reflect the most popular results related to our search.

Results: 61

7. Content filtering:

- o considered only the practitioner literature sources written by software practitioners, software firms or PM related organizations (identified through affiliation or professional qualifications mentioned in the source or through

LinkedIn profile) to ensure context relevancy and avoid promotion of specific tools.

Results: 47

8. Extract data

- o Manually extracted content from the sources to a Google sheet with reference links.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Blog posts, articles on professional networks, and industry reports that has lengthier discussion	Academic publications, short posts, comments, or videos
About GenAI in software project management	GenAI in other industries or other software development roles
Date between 01/12/2022 (after ChatGPT release) to 01/05/2025 (study date)	Publications before December 2022
Language must be English	Written in language other than English
Authored by software practitioners, software firms or PM related organizations	Authored by non-experienced people in software project management domain or articles promoting a specific tool

2. Data Analysis

Then, the selected articles were subjected to qualitative thematic analysis following the Braun and Clarke approach [4]. Articles were first reviewed thoroughly to identify the codes, and later the codes with similar nature were grouped as themes answering the research questions. Some themes were based on deductive coding as expressed directly (some key applications of GenAI in SPM and their benefits, concerns and overcoming strategies, upskilling requirements and sources), whereas some emerged through inductive coding (GenAI in agile SPM, Software PMs perception on GenAI in SPM).

Table 2: Codebook

Main theme	Sub-themes (if applicable)	Codes
GenAI Tools	Prompt-based Tools	ChatGPT, Gemini, Co-pilot
	GenAI Integrations to PM tools	Jira, Trello, Slack, Smartsheet, Asana, MS Project etc.
Key Applications of GenAI in SPM and their benefits	Automation of Routine Tasks	less complex but time-consuming tasks generate project plans, project reports, meeting minutes, follow-up emails Benefits: <i>more time to focus on strategic activities, Efficiency and productivity, Faster deliverables</i>
	Predictive Analytics	risk prediction cost estimations schedule forecasts Benefits: <i>data-driven decision making, better resource allocation, project success</i>
	Communication and Collaboration	AI-powered Chatbots for FAQs Integrations to tools such as Slack Benefits: <i>better task tracking, ease collaboration, better workflow management</i>
		Integrations to tools like Jira (Ex; Atlassian Intelligence, Rovo) <i>PMs are happy to use GenAI in the familiar user-interfaces - No need to switch between tools</i>

	Assist in agile practices	backlog grooming user-story creation story point estimation sprint planning Retrospectives Benefits: <i>Agile project success</i>
Concerns from using GenAI for SPM	Data quality and accuracy	Errors in data or missing some data lead to inaccurate insights Poor prompts lead to poor outcome
	Ethical and privacy concerns	Privacy of client, project or company data Ethical concerns Data protection laws
	Lack of Emotional Intelligence and Human Judgment	GenAI does not have empathy, emotion, human intuition PM need to input those when working with team
Software PMs perception on GenAI in SPM	Positive Perception	Not replace PM role View as an assistant, a co-pilot, a team member or a friend supporting them in their day-to-day activities Must gain awareness of GenAI and upskill themselves Promoter of GenAI to team ("Trailblazers")
Upskilling for PMs in GenAI era	Skills and knowledge requirements in the GenAI era	Prompt Engineering Ethics and data security Human-AI collaboration Emotional Intelligence Strategic and Analytical thinking Learning and adaptability
	Upskilling sources on GenAI for project managers	Online Blogs Videos and Documentations Online certification courses GenAI tools

3. List of Grey Literature Sources

ID	Topic	Year	Source
A1	Can AI Replace Project Managers? The Truth Behind the Hype	2025	LinkedIn
A2	Embracing AI in Project Management	2024	LinkedIn
A3	AI in Agile: How Artificial Intelligence Is Revolutionising the Software Development Lifecycle	2025	LinkedIn
A4	The Evolving Role of Project Managers in an AI-Driven Landscape	2023	Institute Project Management
A5	Shaping the Future of Project Management With AI	2023	PMI
A6	Generative AI for project managers: transforming the way you work	2024	PM-Partners
A7	AI at Work Is Here. Now Comes the Hard Part	2024	Microsoft and LinkedIn survey
A8	First Movers' Advantage: The Immediate Benefits of Adopting Generative AI For Project Management	2024	PMI
A9	Revolutionizing Agile: How AI And GenAI Are Transforming Project Management	2024	Forbes
A10	Pushing the Limits: Transforming Project Management with Generative AI Innovation	2024	PMI
A11	How Generative AI is Revolutionizing Project Management – What Every PM Needs to Know	2025	LinkedIn
A12	Top GenAI Powered Tools for Project Management: How to Choose the Right Fit for Your Project	2024	LinkedIn
A13	How GenAI can transform project management	2023	LinkedIn
A14	Navigating Project Management in the Age of Generative AI	2024	LinkedIn
A15	Embracing Gen AI: Revolutionizing Project Management	2024	LinkedIn
A16	Emerging Impact of Generative AI on Modern Project Management Practices	2024	LinkedIn
A17	Maximize Your Project Management: Potential with GenAI	2024	LinkedIn
A18	GenAI in Project Management: A New Frontier	2024	LinkedIn
A19	Getting Started with Generative AI in Agile Projects	2024	LinkedIn
A20	GenAI's Impact on Agile Project Management	2025	LinkedIn

A21	Knowledge Management in Agile Projects in the GenAI Era	2025	PMI
A22	Gen AI and Agile Development – A Perfect Match for Your Application Transformation	2024	Aspire Systems
A23	GenAI Use Cases in Project Management	2024	Program Strategy HQ
A24	How GenAI is transforming project management?	2024	LinkedIn
A25	AI and Agile: Redefining Project Management in 2024	2024	LinkedIn
A26	Navigating the AI Era: Transforming Project Management with GenAI	2023	LinkedIn
A27	How Large Language Models (LLMs) Can Transform Product Development	2024	LinkedIn
A28	How to Use ChatGPT for Project Management	2024	LinkedIn
A29	Is ChatGPT Safe? AI Do's and Don'ts for Project Managers	2025	AgileMania
A30	How I Transformed ChatGPT Into a Project Management System	2024	How-To-Geek
A31	What Can ChatGPT Do for Project Management?	2023	Institute Project Management
A32	How I Use ChatGPT for Project Planning	2024	Medium
A33	Streamlining Project Management with ChatGPT	2024	Aspects Software
A34	Transform ChatGPT for Effective Project Management	2025	Artificial Intelligence +
A35	Revolutionizing Project Management: How ChatGPT can Enhance Efficiency and Productivity	2024	LinkedIn
A36	Beginner's Guide to Using ChatGPT for IT Project Management	2024	LinkedIn
A37	Enhancing Agile Project Management with ChatGPT: The Power of Conversational AI	2023	LinkedIn
A38	ChatGPT: Project Management Revolutionized with Intelligent Assistance	2023	Resolute Software
A39	AI Co-Pilot for Modern Project Management	2025	LinkedIn
A40	How Copilot Is Changing the Way Project Managers Work in Microsoft 365	2025	LinkedIn
A41	How Microsoft Copilot can support your project management team	2025	MNP Digital

A42	Is Github Copilot's biggest productivity threat bad project management?	2023	zenhub
A43	Generative AI in Agile Project Management: Boosting Efficiency and Adaptability	2025	LinkedIn
A44	The future of agile methodologies with Generative AI	2025	ClearPoint
A45	AI-Driven Agile: How Artificial Intelligence is Reshaping Project Management	2025	SPK and associates
A46	Streamlining Agile Project Management with GenAI for Complex IT Projects	2024	LinkedIn
A47	Agile Project Management Generative AI Uses Cases	2023	LinkedIn

4. Examples for Upskilling sources on GenAI for project managers

Upskilling Source	Examples
Online Blogs, Videos and Documentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copilot for project overview • ChatGPT - Prompts for Project Management and Software Development Methodologies • Beginner's Guide to Using ChatGPT for IT Project Management • How to Use ChatGPT for Project Management • YouTube videos
Online Certification Courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generative AI Overview for Project Managers • Data Landscape of GenAI for Project Managers • Practical Application of Generative AI for Project Managers • Talking to AI: Prompt Engineering for Project Managers • AI for Project Managers and Scrum Masters • AI for Scrum Masters • Scrum Mastery with ChatGPT: Agile Learning with AI • Generative AI for Project Managers and Project Teams • ChatGPT for Project Management - Leveraging AI for Success Specialization • Project Management with ChatGPT: Complete Guide • GitHub Copilot for Project Management • LinkedIn learning courses

5. References

[1] R. Hoda, N. Salleh, and J. Grundy, 'The Rise and Evolution of Agile Software Development', IEEE Softw, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 58–63, 2018, doi: 10.1109/MS.2018.290111318.

- [2] N. Davila, J. Melegati, and I. Wiese, 'Tales From the Trenches: Expectations and Challenges From Practice for Code Review in the Generative AI Era', *IEEE Softw*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 38–45, 2024, doi: 10.1109/MS.2024.3428439.
- [3] R. Hoda, "Basics of Qualitative Data Collection," in *Socio-Technical Grounded Theory*, Springer, Cham, 2024, pp. 141-166.
- [4] Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. Sage